

Review Article

The Making of a Reading Society: How to Reawaken and Sustain the Reading Culture in Nigerian Learners

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Abstract

It has been observed that reading culture among Nigerian children is tragically deficient when compared to the Western world. In this era of high level technological development, this is disheartening such that rather than reading, the younger ones now embrace watching of home video and accessing the internet. This paper focuses on the concept of reading culture, challenges to a reading culture and examination into the strategies to reawakening and sustaining the reading culture in Nigeria learners. The stand point is that efforts should be made by librarians and all stakeholders to bring back the reading culture as this will help to develop our nation, Nigeria.

Keywords: Reading, Reawaken, Reading Culture and Nigerian Learners

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Introduction

Reading is a worldwide phenomenon that has the capacity to promote development as well as instill discipline on the individual. For one to play a significant role in contemporary society, the ability to read and write must be there. The survival of any society, therefore, is a function of the extent to which that society is involved in reading. Reading according to Yilbenalk and Kitgkka (2008) is a basic life skill as well as the cornerstone of a child's success in school and throughout life. Reading, therefore, is an aspect of learning and as such should not be overlooked. Reading as an act plays an

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important role in creating independent learners. Reading is thus indispensable in sustaining the development of any society.

One of the major avenues for acquiring information is reading and reading is the foundation upon which other academic skills are built (Ogbonna and Obiozor, 2009). However, becoming a skilled and adaptable reader according to Igwe (2011) enhances the chances of success at school and beyond. He views reading as not just for school, but for life. He further buttressed that reading in its entire entirety and variety is vital to being better informed, having a better understanding of us as well as others. The importance of reading in a nation's development as pointed out by Mefor (2010) cannot be overlooked. Reading is an essential tool for lifelong learning and is important for everyone to develop the rudiments of reading and the culture of reading always so as to survive in life (Igbokwe, Obidike and Ezeji, 2012).

In spite of the importance of reading as a culture, it has almost entirely disappeared and it has become obvious that Nigerian children no longer read. They only read when they have examination to write, outside that, reading has no meaning to them. Nigerian students hardly make use of the school libraries, in most cases, excuses are that our libraries are not stocked with relevant information sources but the fact remains that the reading culture created early in the twentieth century during the colonial era has been on the decline towards the end of the century (Yilben and Kitgkka, 2008). The school libraries are expected to help in promoting reading culture among Nigerian children. The school administrators and indeed all stakeholders can use various strategies to promote the reading culture. As pointed out by Gbadamosi (2007), reading requires books, it then goes to mean that good reading habit promotes effective use of library book resources and effective use of library book resources has the inherent advantage of promoting good reading habit. Since Nigeria, according to Iloeje, (2014) cannot be regarded as a reading nation because the younger generation of Nigerians does not consider reading a leisure activity; it becomes imperative for libraries to explore various strategies as a means of promoting reading culture.

Concept of Reading Culture

Reading as noted by Anyaemene and Adebola (2011) is a crucial learning activity. Reading according to these authors boosts academic achievement, facilitate knowledge for self-reliance, and equip individuals to function meaningfully and effectively in the scheme of things particularly concerning nation building. This implies that the extent to which a nation develops is a function of the reading culture of the citizens of such nation. It goes to mean that reading is a determining factor for national development. A functionally reading culture as rightly pointed out by Iloeje, (2014) is imperative in this

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age for children who are the future leaders of the nation. He contends that only extensive reading can make the acquisition of knowledge possible because it is through reading that children broaden their understanding of life. In the same vein, according to Gbadamosi (2007) reading culture is the process of building up positive reading attitude among children and students over a period of time. In other words, reading culture is an attitude that is developed over a period of time. Reading culture therefore is not hereditary; hence it does not run through the gene from parents to children. And sadly, reading culture as observed by Yilben and Kitgkka (2008) no longer exist in Nigeria. They assert that the Nigerian child prefer renting films to buying books and when they are tired of watching, they go to cyber cafes to browse the internet. Reading culture in Nigeria therefore is very low compared to developed countries. Ifedili (2009) while x-raying the reading habits of tertiary institution students in Imo state reveals that reading to pass examination, tests, and continuous assessment are the students' topmost reading objectives and purposes in libraries. This revelation also confirms the fact that reading culture does not exist in Nigeria.

Challenges to a Reading Culture

Improving reading culture in children as noted by Ogbonna and Obiozor (2009) is not without constraints. Some of these impediments according to Bello (2006) are:

- (a) inadequate attention to the requirement of the potential readership which suggest a need for pictures, story books and books in local language;
- (b) disregard for the important role of the illustration and designer in the production of book for children;
- (c) the high cost of printing inputs and the desire to keep prices down resulting in unattractive, poor quality children books; and
- (d) inadequate patronage by libraries due to inadequate library resources.

Igwe (2011) attributes part of the constraint to the development of reading culture to literacy apartheid and slavery or literary neo-imperialism, a situation where most of the bookshops in the country prefer to shelve foreign authors against indigenous publications.

Ayanbimpe (2012) identifies unavailability of school libraries and more importantly, lack of funding, for where it exists. Similarly, the state of facilities such as libraries, books, journals and furniture that are helpful for developing a good reading skill and culture are grossly inadequate (Kolawole, 2009). Again, Igwe (2011) pointed out that there is no clear cut policy on funding school libraries and so these libraries are generally ill-equipped lacking proper organization, qualified staff, relevant information resources such as books, and other educational materials.

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However, many reasons according to Iloeje, (2014) has been advanced by analyst for the poor reading culture among Nigerian children, the harsh economic environment is a major constraint militating against reading culture. Similarly, Igwe (2011) citing Gbadamosi (2007) attributed the low level of reading habits and by multi-varied factors and these factors include: change in Nigerian value system, economic hardship that is prevalent in many homes, astronomical prices of books and other information materials as well as cost of publishing books which is very high. In view of the situation relating to reading culture in Nigeria, it is clear that there is need for libraries/school librarians to devise an effective means of promoting reading culture since school library are custodian of school information resources. As rightly captures by Kumar, Ansari and Shukla, (2010), one of the major goals of the school library is to inspire a love for reading in order to promote a reading culture among users. In view of this, libraries/school librarians must make effort to take the book back to the Nigerian child and this can only be achieved if appropriate strategies are devised and applied.

However, Anyachebehi, Anyaeme and Adebola (2011) in their study revealed that the number of strategies use by teachers in Anambra State to teach reading skills are not encouraging and the implication being that learners are not aware of the skills to apply while reading. These apparently have been a problem.

Strategies for Reawakening and Sustaining Reading Culture in Learners

The task of reawakening and sustaining reading culture in Nigeria is for all and sundry viz; the family, teachers, librarians, philanthropists, the media, religious bodies, non-governmental organizations, government etc. The strategies include:

(a) Exposure to books

The first characteristic of an early reading environment is the availability of books and the regular modeling of reading. Ayanbimpe (2012) emphasized that the best way of sustaining reading is the use of informal methods of reading rather than formal methods. He further noted that informal methods stimulate a desire in the child to read before trying to teach him to read. He noted that this is done through storytelling and reading by the teacher and by consulting books to find out things so that children could associate books with pleasure and usefulness. Indeed Ayanbimpe (2012) pointed out that for pupils to be encouraged to read they should be allowed to choose the books they would like to read, to read books with lots of pictures in them, to read for contests, to have a classroom library and to have an author read to them at school. Once pupils are exposed to different practices of reading and reading materials they are likely to broaden their imagination and engage in the practice of regular reading.

Furthermore, access to the text would encourage reading. A starting point is the provision of classroom libraries to the pupils to expose them to a wide range of books, magazines and other print materials in a variety of genres and at various levels of difficulty. Through such activities pupils are likely to become more exposed and encouraged to develop a culture of reading. Iloeje, (2014) suggested that while choice is important, it should be limited so that inexperienced readers are not overwhelmed.

In addition, book fairs, exhibitions and book talks expose pupils and teachers to a variety of information materials. These can be carried out in the school environment whereby teachers and pupils introduce each other to favourite books. This could be done by reading aloud what is on the back cover (blurb), the first paragraph of the first chapter or any favourite part of the story and telling others why the book is enjoyable and later on encouraging swapping of books to boost pupil's morale to read. The promotion of a reading culture in Nigeria, and other African countries, must therefore go hand in hand with the promotion of reading as a pleasurable activity, which means that the pupils must start to read for fun and not just because they have to prepare for examinations (Rosenberg, 2003). Ozo-Eson (2012) stated that, for this to be possible, the promotion of reading for enjoyment, or to 'sell the sizzle of reading' as he puts it, had to begin when the children are very young.

Moreover, it has been noted that a child who viewed reading as entertainment, instead of an activity through which certain skills are taught, would have a more rapid development in relation to literacy. Hence, the promotion of this type of reading is seen as something positive (Rosenberg, 2003). A study comparing high and low achieving countries" revealed facts that could strengthen this view. When students are asked about how one becomes a good reader the answers differ between the best readers in 'the high achieving countries' and the best readers in the 'low achieving countries'. The good readers in the 'high achieving countries' stressed factors like having many good books, having a lively imagination and learning many new words while the bestreaders in the 'low achieving countries' pointed more towards factors like lots of drills, sounding out and self-discipline. Furthermore, the more skill- and drill-based education may not lead to better results. On the contrary, this pedagogy seems to lead to readers that do not read outside school and it does not create engaged readers (Elley, 2001) in order for the reading culture to evolve, reading should be carried out on a regular basis and not necessarily only in schools. Thus, it is interesting to see how possible it is to make children read not just for school purposes but also during their leisure time.

(b) Giving Education priority attention in national human capital development

The improvement and development of reading culture in Nigeria have to start with adequate funding of the education sector. UNESCO has given a minimum benchmark of twenty-six % of a country's national budgets; Nigeria should start from there and the funds should be properly utilized. The greatest resource for development is the human resource, hence no nation can develop in isolation of her human resources; and education is the producer of human resources. So, adequate funding of the sector by all the levels of government will impact positively on libraries, which is the main tool for the development of reading culture (Sarjant, 2005).

(c) Positive emotional associations

Research has shown that children who read with their parents had a higher intelligence, reading ability and better communication skills. According to Iloeje, (2014), reading should be fun and entertaining. Iloeje encourages people never to associate reading with punishment or disciplining their children". For instance, punishing your child by sending him or her to a room to read had a negative effect on his or her interest in reading. Sangkeo (1999) asserted that parents who spent time reading to their children gave them the best possible start on the road to literacy. To him those children who did best in literacy skills at school were those who came from homes where they interacted with books and their parents as well as siblings who read to them. He thus suggested creative ways for parents to foster the reading habits among children and these included reading story books aloud, creating a learning environment by setting up a home library, and visiting libraries and bookshops, among others.

(d) Rewarding pupils and teachers

Studies revealed that teachers rewarded pupils who had performed even moderately well in reading with small tokens like sweets or biscuits. Some of the ways in which teachers reward their pupils are through showing off the pupil's books to their fellow pupils, asking pupils to read in front of the class and putting stars in the pupil's exercise books. Such rewards encouraged pupils to indulge more in reading since they anticipate being rewarded. Teachers in return are rewarded by their head teachers, depending on the pupils' performance in class.

(e) Availing relevant literature

The relevance of the material depended on the context and the children. The best judges of what material is stimulating and relevant for children, are the children themselves (Magara, 2005). When children get the opportunity to select their own books based on their own needs, it could make them become more interested and engaged in reading.

This is important since this children's own interest and engagement are vital components of a good learning environment and the ability to promote a reading culture. Although it is stated that the best way to promote reading as an enjoyable activity is to let the children choose the books they want to read by themselves, this is not always possible (Uhegbu, 2007).

In most cases, when children are allowed to choose books they still have to pick from a limited selection. Thus, it is interesting to see on what grounds these books are selected. In most of the literature that we come across, it is stressed that books should be selected with the specific context in mind. It is acknowledged that developing countries required books printed in local languages which reflect local knowledge, traditions and culture (Ifedili, 2009). Books that dealt with subjects that are relevant to the children's daily lives and reflect their world both inside and outside school are also believed to promote and engage readers (Ayanbimpe, 2012).

Furthermore, to be able to produce culturally suitable books, local publishers should be involved in the production of books for children in developing countries. The importance of local publishers is not only related to the production of culturally suitable books for children, it could also be seen as a way of preventing cultural imperialism (Elley, 2001). Apart from books that dealt with the everyday experience of children in Africa, it is also important to consider the African heritage when writing and selecting books that are relevant for children.

(f) Time for practice

Early readers have been characteristically left alone to look at books and practice reading-like behaviors that have been modeled for them and no one monitors their efforts to read or pressures them to sound it out (Ayanbimpe 2012). Isaac (2007) noted that adults who offer to read to young children often helped them to develop as independent readers by engaging them in conversation about what they had read. This is why Redford (2011), as referred to by Nnam, (2003) recommended that in order to sustain the reading habit in schools, reading should be taught as a subject in its own right, regularly and systematically, and therefore a lot of time must be specially allocated on the timetable for it. Nnam (2003) emphasized that schools should put in place policies, routines and curricula that require pupils to visit the library at least once a week.

Teachers gave students assignments that required library research to encourage them to read ahead and expand on what they had learnt in class. Through the use of planned reading sessions, pupils would be able to utilise the time they got to visit the libraries

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and get exposed to a wide variety of reading materials, which would encourage them to engage in reading. In addition, Isaac (2007) emphasized that as a means to promote reading among pupil's reading logs should be introduced. The reading logs help pupils to note their reading activities inside and outside of class. They include what is read; how long it is read or how many pages are read. The logs not only serve as an adequate reminder to read, but they also convey a strong and clear message about the importance of reading outside of class and provide a structure for tracking progress. Through such an activity pupils are likely to be encouraged to read more.

(g) Establishment of National Commission for Libraries (NCL)

This commission, when established, will cater for the growth, development, coordination and services of various zonal and regional branches of the National Library of Nigeria in different states of the federation.

(h) Establishment of State Commission for Libraries (SCL) throughout the 36 states of the federation and the FCT.

The commission will be responsible for the growth, development, coordination and services of library branches in the local government areas of the state. There should be the establishment of libraries in all the local government areas of the respective states. Each local government should have a Director of Library Services who will establish a library where there is none and coordinate all the public primary and secondary school (Phan, 2006).libraries under the local government. Professional librarians should be made the Directors of Local Government Library Services. They should ensure that each of the primary and secondary school libraries has a professional librarian or at least an education graduate with a certificate or diploma in librarianship. The essence of this specific qualification is to have competent librarian(s) that will be able to plan, develop and execute result-oriented information literacy education.

(i) Integration of Information Literacy Education in the curriculum of secondary schools and in the tertiary institutions as an independent General Studies Course with units/credits allotted to it

In primary schools there is the teaching of reading and writing. As a continuation, there should be the inclusion of Information Literacy Education as a subject in the curriculum of secondary schools. Information literacy has to do with the ability to recognize when information is needed and how to locate, evaluate, effectively use and communicate information in its various formats. Its aim is to use the techniques and skills for utilizing the wide range of information materials and tools to solve problems (Etim, 2008, p. 73).

At the tertiary level, Information Literacy Education (Library User Education) is equally neglected. According to Eze (2004) many Nigerian Universities such as the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, University of Lagos, and Enugu State University of Science and Technology still integrate library user education with courses. In Abia State University Uturu, it is part of Use of English, which is a General Studies Course. The same is equally applicable to Bayero University Kano and University of Abuja where it is included as part of the general studies programme. Some others like the University of Ibadan organize an hour lecture and guided tour of the library, including Library Weeks, which are spread over a month after which students are deemed to have mastered the techniques of library utilization. When these students are bombarded with lectures and they rush to the library to source information, their manner of approach to the library and its information materials speaks volumes of poor knowledge of library user education. There is urgent need to make Library User Education or Information Literacy Education an independent General Studies Course in all tertiary institutions in the country with units not less than two allotted to it. And its teaching should be handled by professional academic librarians who are experts in the field.

(j) Creation of library periods in School Timetable

Library utilization periods should be included in the time table of primary and secondary schools. It should be in such a way that at least a class (for instance primary 1 or Junior Secondary 1) will have two hour in a week for library use. In boarding schools, evening prep time is for the students general reading a form of literacy exercise, which is usually between 4-5 pm, should be set aside for library use. Primary one to six and secondary one to six are to share the days from Mondays to Saturdays respectively. This is practiced in Thomas Adewumi International College Oko, Kwara State. During the period, the library staff properly supervises students. This is an instrument of reading culture development.

(k) State Government should establish state-of-the-art publishing firms

When established, these publishing firms should encourage the effort of our indigenous authors. The state publishing firm should encourage scholarship and creativity by charging lesser in publishing of materials. Specific copies of these published books should be distributed to public schools (in their libraries) in the respective states bearing in mind the relevance of such materials with respect to the development of the students' reading habit.

(1) **Establishment of family libraries**

Parents have a role to play in the development of the reading habit of their children. Eyo (2007) revealed that 70 % of the problem associated with the poor reading culture of our children is traceable to many social and environmental factors, including parents. Parents and guardians should always monitor what their children and wards do. Children are spending more time these days watching television and using other electronic gadgets like computers. Too many of our young people, watching movies have become an addiction, with the result that many children and even adults consider reading an ordeal. Children can only benefit optimally from electronic technology when they are firmly established as readers. The view that school and children's libraries should be deployed with ICT facilities as the only way of enabling children to be in touch with information is a tragically mistaken policy that is likely to decrease literacy rather than advance it. Michael Gorman, an experienced British Librarian bluntly states that it is literacy that is the major enabling technology in the development of reason, logic, systematic thinking and research (Eyo, 2007), while inadequate skills of many students accepted into higher education today are the products of a society and a school system that has de-emphasized basic skills, including the most basic skills of all: reading and writing. Let me share the experience of Dr. Reuben Abati of the Guardian Newspaper at the 50th anniversary of Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* in order to buttress my point.

I was in Abuja the other week as compared of an evening of readings put together by the Federal Capital Territory administration. I was astounded when a young lady, a final year English Studies undergraduate, in a private conversation, could not establish the link between Chinua Achebe and *Things Fall Apart*. She insisted that Pete Edochie wrote *Things Fall Apart* and that the man in fact played the role of Okonkwo on television. She has never read the novel but she has watched the television series based on the novel and, Edochie who acted the lead role had made an impression on her as the author. I had to give her my copy of the Heinemann 50th anniversary edition of the novel, to purge her of her crime (Abati, 2008)

Parents should establish private libraries at home in order to encourage the reading habit of their children. A large room in the house can be set-aside for this. It should be provided with shelves and reading desks. Then purchase of books for the library should

be done gradually as the information needs of the children grow. A parent can buy at least five books in a week, and in one year, the family will have a sizeable library that will cater for the information needs of the family.

(m) Philanthropists and other spirited individuals should come up with the establishment of non-governmental organizations for promoting reading culture.

The efforts of such NGOs like the African Center for Reading and Development, Port Harcourt, City Profs Academy, Lagos etc in providing mobile library services as well as increasing reading awareness in the public schools are commendable. Also, spirited individuals can donate books to our school and public libraries in order to encourage reading habits.

(n) Media houses like radio, television and newspaper and publishing firms are equal stakeholders in this course.

Radio and television houses can contribute by airing promoting reading habit jingles whereas newspaper houses can advertise things that will stimulate reading.

(o) Institutionalization of Scholarship Schemes by State Governments

The governors of the 36 states of Nigeria and FCT should implement scholarship schemes in the secondary and tertiary levels of education including postgraduate studies at national and overseas.

(p) Formulation and implementation of a viable National Information Policy (NIP).

According to Gbaje (2007), the Nigerian government approved a national information technology policy in March 2001. The implementation started in April 2001 with the establishment of the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), whose mission was “to use Information Technology for education, creation of wealth, poverty eradication, job creation and global competitiveness”. According to the policy, the government will set up and develop a national information infrastructure backbone as the gateway to the global information infrastructure and create state as well as local area networks (Womboh, 2008). Some years after the establishment of NITDA, Uhegbu (2007) cites the unstable nature of Nigeria’s economic and political environment; government’s apathy towards information infrastructure, resources and services; weak and uncoordinated information professional associations in the country; oral medium of communication and high illiteracy rate; underdeveloped and deficient information facilities within the country and frequent interference in the functions of the country’s information institutions as some of the problems hindering the implementation of a result-oriented national information policy. Nigerian government had acknowledged

the failure of NITDA, and has put in place a mechanism to review the IT policy (Gbaje, 2007).

However, in reviewing the policy for a viable national information policy, there is need for proper assessment, planning and implementation. A national information policy according to Uhegbu (2007, p. 250) is a road map to sustainable and balanced flow of information in all sectors of the economy, proper development of our information infrastructures, appropriate and reliable information packaging for human resources development. It will also encourage standards in the establishment, maintenance and operation of information infrastructures such as libraries, publishing firms, information resource centres, telecommunication companies, information technology driven establishments etc. This will play a significant role in fighting illiteracy and will be geared towards fostering reading habit among Nigerians.

Conclusion

There is no gainsaying the fact that the development of our reading habits and culture will improve the nation's human resources that will champion the much-expected sustainable development. Massive investment in improving access to books through public institutions such as schools and libraries is a matter of absolute urgency. Books and libraries are essential especially in this information age where knowledge and information have acquired the materiality of capital and commodity, whose uneven accumulation will dictate the wealth of countries or otherwise. In order to achieve a total national consciousness of the value and benefits of reading, all stakeholders in the reading chain which include writers, publishers, booksellers, the media, teachers at all levels, librarians, civil societies, the corporate sector, religious bodies, community based organizations, non-governmental organizations, governments at all levels etc. Must support and participate actively in this clarion call.

References

Adebola, (2011). The place of libraries in promoting reading habits among Nigerian Youths. Paper presented at the national conference of the Nigerian Library association (NLA), at Enugu, Enugu State.

Anyachebelu, F.E, Anyamene, A. and Adebola, H.E (2011). Strategies for promoting reading skills for the educational development of learners in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy studies (JETERAPS), 2(4): 211-215

Ayanbimpe, S. (2012). Reading culture has totally collapsed in Nigeria-Librarian. Leadership Newspaper. April 5.

Bello, N. (2006). Reading Skills: the role of teaching techniques and library services in Nigeria. *Library, Archival and Information Science Journal* 5 (2): 103-109.

Elley, W.B. (2001). Literacy in the present world: Realities and possibilities. In Verhoeven, Ludo and Snow, Catherine. (2004). *Literacy and Motivation: Reading engagement in individuals and groups*. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.

Etim, F.E. (2008). Information Literacy in an Information Age. In F.E. Etim & F.U. Nssien. (2010). *Information Literacy for Library Search*. Uyo: Abaam Publishing.

Eyo, W. (2007). Nigeria: Libraries and Reading Culture. *This Day*, February 11, 2007.

Eze, C.C. (2004). The Need for effective teaching of the Use of Library in Nigerian Universities. *The Nigerian Library Link*. II (I), 67-74.

Gbadamosi, T. (2007). Library reading culture and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Oyo State. *Middle-belt Journal of Library and Information Science* 7(2):42-58

Gbaje, E.S (2007). Implementing a National Virtual Library for higher institutions in Nigeria. LIBRES: *Library and Information Science Research Electronic Journal* 17 (2). www.libres.curtin.edu.au/libres17n2/Gbaje_2007.

Igbokwe, J.C., Obidike, N.A. and Ezeji, E.C. (2012). Influence of electronic media on reading ability of school children. Available online at: <http://unllib.unl.edu/lpp>

Igwe, K.N. (2011). Reading culture and Nigeria's quest for sustainable development. Library Available online at: <http://unllib.unl.edu/lpp>

Ifedili, C. J. A. (2009). An assessment of reading culture among students in Nigerian tertiary institutions: a challenge to educational managers. Available at www.libres.curtin.edu.au/libres17n2/Ifedili_2017

Iloeje, M. U. (2014). Restoring reading culture and use of library among young Nigerian adults: implications for empowering the citizens and Nigerian society. Keynote paper read at the national conference of the Philosophy and Practice (on-line journal). Available online at: [http://www.webpage.uidaho.edu/mboline.Nigerian Library Association held at Enugu](http://www.webpage.uidaho.edu/mboline.Nigerian_Library_Association_held_at_Enugu).

Isaac, B. (2007). The 26 major advantages to reading more books and why 3 in every 4 people are being shut out of success. www.persistenceunlimited.com/.../the-26-major-advantages-to-reading Accessed on 19th May, 2017.

Kolawole, A. (2009) Reading habits of senior secondary students at Allahabad City, U.P., India. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. (online journal) Available online at <http://www.webpages.uidaho.edu/mbohir/kumar-ansarishukla.htm>. 4/28/2017.

Magara, E. (2005). Towards a school library development policy for Uganda. *Library Review*, 53 (6) pg 70-76.

Mefor, C. (2010). Nigeria: reading culture – the present and future of National Development. Available online at: <http://allafrican.com/stories>.

Nnam, J. (2003). Promoting the reading culture in secondary schools: A case study of Mengo senior school. Unpublished dissertation East African School of Library and Information Science, Makerere University: Kampala.

Ogbonna, A.U. and Obiozor, R.N. (2009). Strategies for improving reading culture in children in Anambra State. *Anambra State Library and Information Digest*, 3(5), 24-33.

Ozo-Eson, P. I. (2012). *African society and culture: our heritage*. Abuja: Ugwu Publishing Co.

Redford, K. (2011). Classroom strategies: creating a reading culture for struggling readers. dyslexia.yale.edu/edu_culture4readers-htm Accessed on 30th November, 2014.

Rosenberg, D. (2003). *Reader development and ready promotion: recent experiences from seven countries in Africa*. Oxford: International Network for the Availability of Scientific publications.

Shukla, (2010). Dynasties of poverty and the education challenge. The Nigerian Village Square. www.nigerianvillagesquare.org.

Sangkeo, (1999). The State of Reading in selected Secondary Schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. *African Research Review* 3 (1):388-398.

Yilbena, J.J. and Kitgkka, G. (2008). Revolutionary secondary school students reading habits for better academic performance. *Nigerian Journal of Sociology of Education* 2(2): 222-226

Uhegbu, A.N. (2007). *The information user: Issues and themes*. Okigwe: Whytem Publishers.

Womboh, B.S.H (2008). The state of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Nigerian University Libraries. The Experience of Ibrahim Babangida Library Federal University of Technology Yola Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal online), 2017.